

Phytochemical Screening, Antibacterial and Antioxidant Activities of *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* Wild & T. Durand (Gentianaceae) Originated from Democratic Republic of the Congo

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ABSTRACT

Anthocleista liebrechtsiana is a plant species widely used in traditional medicine to treat bacterial infections. To provide a scientific basis to traditional uses of this plant species, its different extracts were evaluated for their antibacterial and antioxidant potential. Antibacterial activity was assessed using minimum inhibitory concentration. The presence of phytoconstituents was detected qualitatively. *A. liebrechtsiana* extracts displayed interesting antibacterial and antioxidant activities. The Gram positive bacteria *S. aureus* ATCC 33591 were more sensitive to *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* than the Gram negative *E. coli* ATCC 27195. All the extracts tested were found to be biologically active against *Staphylococcus aureus* except alcoholic extract of the leaves for which the bioactivity was moderate. The antibacterial activity was marked for the stem bark extracts (MIC \leq 31.5 μ g/mL) than those of the leaves (MIC \leq 62.5 μ g/mL). Methanol extract of *A. liebrechtsiana* displayed also interesting free radical Scavenging activity (IC₅₀ < 10 μ g/mL). Phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of total polyphenols, catechic tannins, alkaloids, saponins, terpenes and steroids. Antibacterial and free radical scavenging efficacy shown by this plant provides a scientific basis and thus, validates its traditional use as phytomedicine. Isolation and purification of different phytochemicals may further yield significant antibacterial and antioxidant agents.

Keyword: Traditional medicine, *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana*, bacterial infections, antioxidant activity, Democratic Republic of the Congo

INTRODUCTION

The increase of antibiotic resistance by the pathogenic microorganisms to conventional drugs has necessitated the search for new, efficient and cost effective drugs for the control of infectious diseases. Several reports have shown that

the medicinal plants constitute a great source of biologically active drugs for the control of pathogenic organisms [1-5].

Microbial infections, especially due to *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus* and *Pseudomonas* species, and the presence of

oxygen free radicals, are known impediments to wound healing [6]. It is also known that, infections are recurrent pathologies of the Sick Cell Disease (SCD) and remain the leading cause of death in children patients. In SCD, *Staphylococcus aureus* is the bacteria most implicated in septicemia and osteomyelitis, while some serotypes of *Escherichia coli* (K1) are able of causing very serious neonatal infections that are potentially complicated by meningitis or septicemia [7, 8]. Any agent capable of eliminating or reducing the number of microorganisms, as well as reducing the level of reactive oxygen species (ROS), may facilitate the wound healing process or useful for SCD patients. It then becomes necessary to search for new antimicrobial and antioxidant drugs, especially those that would be cheap and thus easily affordable by poor population.

The present study was performed with the aim of evaluating the antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of different extracts of *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* Wild & T. Durand (Synonym: *Anthocleista baertsiana* De Wild. & T. Durand; *A. gossweileri* Exell). The decoction of this plant species is taken to treat venereal diseases in Democratic Republic of the Congo.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material collection and identification

The tested plant materials (stem bark and leaves) used in this study were collected in Democratic Republic of the Congo during a field work in March 2011 and were authenticated by Mr B.L. Nlandu of the INERA (Institut National d'Etudes et Recherches Agronomiques). Vouchers specimens are on deposit at the INERA Herbarium of the Faculty of Science (Université de Kinshasa).

Extraction and chemical screening

The dried and powdered plant material (10 g) was repeatedly extracted by cold percolation with 95% ethanol (EtOH) and water (100 mL x 2) for 48 hours. Chemical screening was done in aqueous and organic extract according to a well known protocol as previously reported. Fractions were filtered and concentrated to dryness under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator [9].

Preparation of methanol extract and increasing polarity extracts

Each plant powder (100 g) was macerated in methanol 80% (1L x 2) for 48 hours. After filtering the mixture, the aqueous-methanolic filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator. The methanolic extract was suspended in distilled water and sequentially partitioned with n-hexane, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, ethanol, and methanol (1:1, v/v) three times at room temperature. The resulting fractions were evaporated to dryness on an evaporator apparatus. All extracts were stored at +4 °C.

Antioxidant assay

The DPPH free radical (1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) scavenging assay was performed as previously reported [10-12]. The radical scavenging activity of extracts for DPPH free radical was measured based on the principle of the reduction of the DPPH radical to a yellow-colored compound (diphenyl picrylhydrazin) in the presence of an antioxidant; the extent of the reaction depending on the hydrogen donating ability of the antioxidant. Briefly, a 100 µM solution of DPPH radical in methanol was prepared. 3,5 mL of this solution was added to 0,5 mL solution of each extract in methanol at concentrations ranging from 0,1 to 1 mg/mL, thus obtaining the desired final concentrations in the reaction mixture. The mixture was shaken vigorously and incubated in the dark at room temperature for 30 min. The absorbance was measured at 515 nm using a spectrophotometer

SP- 1105 Brand model. Methanol was used as a blank. The control solution consists of 0,5 mL of methanol and 3,5 mL of DPPH radical solution. The antiradical activity of a sample (calculated by the following formula) is given as percentage of reduced DPPH free radical: %I = [(OD control - OD sample)/OD control] × 100. The IC₅₀ value (µg/mL) is the effective concentration at which DPPH radicals were scavenged by 50%. L-ascorbic acid was used as positive control. Duplicate analyses were run for each extract.

Antibacterial evaluation

2.6.1. Microbial strains

The activity of the plant samples was tested toward *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus* ATCC 25923) and *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli* ATCC 25922). The tested strains were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Rockville MD, USA).

2.6.2. Determination of Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC)

MIC was determined by broth micro-dilution method as previously reported [1]. The inocula of microorganisms were prepared from 24 hours old broth cultures. The absorbance was read at 600 nm and adjusted with sterile physiological solution to match that of a 0.5 McFarland standard solution. From the prepared microbial solutions, other dilutions with sterile physiological solution were prepared to give a final concentration of 10⁶ colony-forming units (CFU) per milliliter. Stock solutions of the extracts were prepared in 0.1% (v/v) aqueous tween 80 (Fisher chemicals) at concentrations of 1 mg/mL. The two-fold serial dilutions in concentrations of the extracts were prepared in Mueller Hinton Broth (MHB) (Conda, Madrid, Spain) to give final concentrations ranging from 250 to 1.95 µg/mL.

An aliquot (10 µL) of a 10⁶ CFU/mL overnight culture was added to wells of a sterile 96-well micro-plate titer. The positive control wells contained MHB+ bacteria suspension without plant extract while negative control wells contained MHB only. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined as the lowest plant extract concentration at which no growth were observed after 24 hours. MTT (30 µL) in aqueous solution (0.01%) was used to evaluate the micro-organism viability. For minimum bactericidal (MBC) determination, 10 µL was taken from each well of complete inhibition of bacterial growth after incubation and spot inoculated on MHB and incubated for 72 hours at 37 °C. The concentration at which no growth observed on subculture was determined as the MBC.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical screening

The results of chemical screening *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* are presented in Table 1.

It is deduced from the table 1 that leaves and stem bark of *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* contain total polyphenols, catechic tannins, alkaloids, saponins, terpenes and steroids. However, we also note that phenolic compounds such as anthocyanins, leuco-anthocyanins, flavonoids, gallic tanins, and coumarins and quinones are not found in these two plant organs.

The presence of various secondary metabolites in the plant could justify its medical use. Indeed, *A. liebrechtsiana* is reported to treat azoospermia, hepatitis and venereal disease [13]. Compounds, which are significantly present in the plant, are well known for their large spectrum of pharmacological properties, including antimicrobial (alkaloids and saponins) and antioxidant (tannins) activities [14-17]

Table 1: Chemical screening of *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana*

Chemical groups	<i>Anthocleista liebrechtsiana</i>	
	Stem bark	Leaves
Total polyphenols	+	+
Anthocyanins	-	-
Leuco-anthocyanins	-	-
Flavonoids	-	-
Gallic tannins	-	-
Catechic tannins	+	+
Coumarines	-	-
Quinones	-	-
Alkaloids	+	+
Saponins	+	+
Terpenes and steroids	+	+

Extraction yields

Extraction yields of *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* stem bark (left) and leaves (right) are given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Extraction yields of *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* stem bark (left) and leaves (right)

According to the results presented in figure 1, it is clearly shown that the unpolar solvents have fewer yields than polar ones. Indeed, methanol gives a high output; and poor yield is obtained with dichloromethane. This reveals that the abundant metabolites in *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* are those which pass easily through the polar solvents. The extraction yields of plant are 1.7% (methanol), 0.4% (ethyl acetate and n-hexane) and 0.3% (dichloromethane) for the stem bark and 1.9% (methanol), 1.6% (ethyl acetate), 1.5% (n-hexane) and 0.9% (dichloromethane) for the leaves. Leaves were found to contain more secondary metabolites than the stem bark. This difference in the compounds content of plant organs can be explained by the fact that leaves are the site of biochemical pathways of photosynthesis and naturally occurring secondary metabolites synthesis [18].

Antibacterial activity

The antimicrobial activity of extracts from *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* strains was determined. The results are shown in Tables 2 and 3. From the table 2, it can be deduced that all the extracts tested are biologically active against *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 33591 strains except alcoholic extract of the leaves for which the bioactivity was moderate. The antibacterial activity was marked

for the stem bark extracts than those of the leaves. This activity was found to be bactericidal.

From the table 3, it can be deduced that n-hexane and dichloromethane soluble fractions of the stem bark and leaves and the ethyl acetate and methanol soluble fraction of the leaves of *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* displayed moderate activity against *E. Coli* ATCC 27195 strains.

The present study revealed that the Gram positive bacteria *S. aureus* were more sensitive to *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* than the Gram negative *E. coli*. The higher sensitivity of Gram-positive bacteria could be attributed to their outer peptidoglycan layer which is not an effective permeability barrier. Gram-negative bacteria having an outer phospholipidic membrane carrying the structural lipopolysaccharide components make the cell wall impermeable to lipophilic solutes while porins constitute a selective barrier to hydrophilic solutes with an exclusion limit of 600 Da [19].

The present findings indicate that *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* could serve as promising source of antimicrobials. Historically, Plants and microbial pathogens have been living together for many centuries. In such co-evolution, plants develop elegant and numerous biochemical defense strategies to counter the microorganisms attack by producing specialized secondary

metabolites that have toxic effect on the microbes. These bactericidal/bacteriostatic and anti-infective naturally occurring compounds are used as medicines [20]. Indeed, despite the fact that plant pathogenic microorganisms have played a key role in the early evolution of the secondary metabolites diversity, there is little chance for a microbe to gain resistance from a plant as it is

known for antibiotic-producing microbes which possess genes protecting them from the toxic effects of these compounds. Like microbial antibiotics, plant antimicrobial secondary metabolites could kill pathogenic agent via a non-species specific mechanism such as disrupting microbial cell membranes or inhibiting quorum sensing phenomena [21].

Table 2: Inhibitory effect of *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* extracts against *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 33591 (expressed as the minimum inhibitory concentration MIC and the minimum bactericidal concentration MBC).

Used parts	MIC/MBC ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)			
	<i>Anthocleista liebrechtsiana</i> extract			
	n-Hexane	Dichloromethane	Ethyl acetate	Methanol
Stem bark	31,25/62,5	31,25/62,5	15,625/31,25	7,812/31,25
Leaves	31,25/62,5	62,5/125	62,5/125	125/250

Table 3: Inhibitory effect of *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* extracts against *E. Coli* ATCC 27195 (expressed as the minimum inhibitory concentration MIC and the minimum bactericidal concentration MBC).

Used parts	MIC/MBC ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)			
	<i>Anthocleista liebrechtsiana</i> extract			
	n-Hexane	Dichloromethane	Ethyl acetate	Methanol
Stem bark	125/250	125/125	62,5/250	62,5/125
Leaves	125/250	125/250	125/250	125/250

Antioxidant activity

The radical scavenging activity of different fractions is given in Table 4.

Table 4: Radical scavenging activity of some fractions from *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana*

Fraction	IC ₅₀ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Free radical Scavenging Activity
L-Ascorbic Acid (Positive control)	0.56 \pm 0.21	1.79
Leaves MeOH extract	1.80 \pm 0.05	0.56
Stem bark MeOH extract	4.70 \pm 0.32	0.21

MeOH methanol

As it can be noticed from Table 4, methanol extract of *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* displayed interesting free radical Scavenging activity ($IC_{50} < 10 \mu\text{g/mL}$). But, compared to the positive control (high antioxidant activity) this activity was weak while leaves extract displayed high activity than the stem bark.

The production of free radicals within the cells is the common denominator of the chronic and infectious diseases [22]. An herbal drug presenting at the same time antibacterial and antioxidant properties can be useful for the management of such diseases.

CONCLUSION

The overall results of the present study provided evidence for the antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of studied plant extracts, and bring supportive data for future investigations that will lead to the use of standardized herbal medicine from *Anthocleista liebrechtsiana* in oxidative stress induced disease such as SCD and antimicrobial therapy.

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